

Preparing the Research & Innovation Core for Mission Ocean, Seas & Waters

Deliverable D2.2

Mission Ocean Communication Strategy

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Executive Summary

This Mission Ocean Communication Strategy aims to provide PREP4BLUE and other EC-funded Mission Ocean partners with the tools and resources necessary for articulating “Mission Restore our Oceans and Waters by 2030” (also known as the Mission or Mission Ocean) while also engaging and inspiring partners, stakeholders, citizens, etc. to commit to the goals and ambitions espoused. The Mission aims to build on and connect the many existing projects and initiatives at the EU, national, and local levels - and inspire awe and wonder around the ocean, connecting people with things they deeply

value while welcoming and eliciting interest in taking action. The Mission will encompass hundreds of contributions from different communities across Europe, and its implementation will thus require a number of institutions, platforms, and processes. Some of these will be physical entities while others will be more conceptual and abstract - including, for example, Lighthouses, citizen assemblies, Blue Parks, EU/non-EU funded projects, etc. WP2’s goal is to work with a variety of these stakeholders to help ensure communications on behalf of Mission Ocean are inspiring, engaging, and on brand.

PREP4BLUE is the first project (Coordinated Support Action [CSA]) funded under Horizon Europe to support the Mission. PREP4BLUE’s overarching objective is to develop the R&I implementation modalities required to achieve the Mission objectives and to facilitate a successful first phase (2022-2025) of the Mission Ocean. This project’s outcomes should allow the Lighthouses to develop and pilot innovation of all forms: technological, social, business models, and governance with an emphasis on the methodologies that will allow co-design/co-implementation of solutions with citizens and stakeholders.

As part of PREP4BLUE Work Package 2 (WP2: Creating a Visionary Narrative, Communications and Spaces), the German Marine Research Consortium (KDM) is tasked with delivering artifacts and tools for Mission partners that can be used as part of the broader communication, dissemination, and exploitation strategy, including using social media, a website, events, etc. to spark engagement and commitment to the Mission.

This communication strategy contains a variety of information meant to guide Mission partners in clearly articulating the Mission and their related work through inspiring and motivational content and messaging while adhering to established best practices and branding. Partners are welcome and encouraged to use this information in their communications efforts and to involve PREP4BLUE WP leaders when developing communications and outreach activities as part of the broader Mission strategy to mobilize and engage the public across all platforms.

Questions, comments, and/or concerns about this document should be emailed to engage@missionoceanwaters.eu, subject line “PREP4BLUE D2.2 Communications Strategy”.

1 Introduction

WP2 is tasked with building a community around and for the Mission through communications, and D2.2: Mission Ocean Communication Strategy is one of many helpful tools WP2 will provide in that capacity. While PREP4BLUE/WP2 is not the “official” communication platform for the Mission (the EC is), WP2’s pilot communications work should serve as catalyst for Mission Ocean growth and engagement while aiding the basin CSAs and other projects in their specific communications efforts.

1.1 D2.2 Background & Scope

PREP4BLUE partners were not aware that a comprehensive corporate design, communications plan, graphics, guidelines, etc. for the Mission had already been drafted for the EC when WP2 drafted its proposed tasks and deliverables. Therefore, many of the tasks and deliverables proposed as part of the original WP2 workplan are already established and in use by the EC. This rendered some of WP2’s efforts duplicative and unnecessary, thereby altering the focus and scope of this deliverable, D2.2 (e.g., WP2 would no longer create a corporate design).

Rather than duplicate assets that the EC has already created, and which they have requested Mission Ocean partners (including PREP4BLUE partners) use, this communication strategy details the specific communications work and products WP2 will provide. It also details those created by the EC for use by all Mission Ocean partners, and to some extent the public, with the hope of ensuring consistent branding and messaging by all EC-funded Mission Ocean stakeholders. The collective array of various tools and assets are meant to support and aid PREP4BLUE and other Mission Ocean stakeholders in engaging citizens, sharing successes, and contributing to the overall goals and ambitions of Mission Ocean while staying true to a unified look, voice, and feel. They are meant to be used in complimentary fashion, and this strategy should help ensure partners have access to and instructions for using available tools and assets to communicate the Mission.

Furthermore, because contractual/legal limitations hinder the types of communication/coordination PREP4BLUE can have with the EC, WP2 is not able to work with them as envisaged. There are ongoing discussions with the EC project officer and others on how to ensure our efforts are collaborative moving forward, especially as the Mission Ocean Implementation Support Platform (MOISP) is engaged. Therefore, WP2 is attempting to go beyond the original scope of the tasks and deliverables to provide additional communications tools (Digital Academy, etc.) in an effort to further assist our partners in reaching their communications goals while not duplicating, contradicting, or conflicting with assets the EC has already created.

Communication Strategy (D2.2)

“Working with the EC, and the Mission implementation platform, T2.2 will prepare the overarching Mission Communication Strategy (D2.2), including branding elements such as the corporate design for the mission, Narrative Guide elements, and incorporating social/digital media. The work will be structured in the following steps: scoping, research (e.g., mapping perceptions and types of mission contributions), analysis, and pilot test. A branding guidebook with multimedia elements will be produced; subsequent deliverables could include subchapters for replicability to use across future networks. It will propose inspirational and emblematic science and innovation-based images and messages to aid Mission communication goals, including visualizing narrative (T2.1).”

1.2 WP2 Communication Strategy Goals & Related Actions

WP2 COMMUNICATION STRATEGY GOAL	RELATED ACTION(S)
Clearly and effectively communicate the Mission, including its goals, success stories, calls to action, events, etc. via a variety of channels and methods	Provide a dynamic public website and engaging social media channels that PREP4BLUE and Basin CSA partners (and in some cases other stakeholders/public) can contribute to
Promote the Mission Charter and encourage entities to sign and commit to it	Actively feature calls for signatories on social media, the website, and at events. Offer promotion of signatories on various channels as well as possible access to services (training, etc.)
Support the EC by using and promoting amongst stakeholders the already established EC Mission Ocean branding and assets to help ensure a unified voice, look, and feel for the Mission	Provide relevant documents, guidelines, and assets for partners to assist with their own communications via personalized log-in on the website
Assist partners with their communications in support of the various narratives via the website, social media, events, etc.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Solicit stories and run features and campaigns for partners/stakeholders to spotlight their Mission endeavors, successes, etc. (Ocean superstars, use of MoJo, etc.) 2) Offer training through the Mission Ocean Digital Academy (for relevant partners/charter signatories - accessed via the website) and story/event coverage
Align our events and campaigns with relevant Mission Ocean activities/partners to further embed their impact in society at large and promote the Mission	Work with the EC and Mission actors, especially the basin CSAs, on creation and hosting of two events
PROTOCOL FOR PREP4BLUE PARTNERS & OTHER EC-FUNDED MISSION OCEAN PARTNERS	
PREP4BLUE, basin CSAs, EC-funded Mission Ocean partners, and even the public can/should inform KDM of their planned Mission Ocean outreach activities, success stories, social media posts, campaigns, projects, events, etc. so they may be considered for sharing, feature stories, website content, public calendar, etc. which are accessible to all partners. Email engage@missionoceanwaters.eu for details.	
COMMUNICATIONS COLLABORATIVE	
Led by WP2, the Communications Collaborative helps facilitate information sharing between PREP4BLUE partners, basin CSAs, the Mission Ocean Implementation Support Platform (MOISP), and other EC-funded stakeholders to ensure all parties have the necessary and proper information, tools, and assets for enhanced communication of Mission activities. The Collaborative's format may evolve when the MOISP's work structure is further clarified. Email engage@missionoceanwaters.eu for details.	

1.3 Partners Involved

Official contributing partners to WP2 deliverables include ERINN, UCC, CPMR, FHG, CSIC, and NRI. However, for this specific deliverable there were no assigned collaborators. Instead, feedback was solicited from members of the newly established Communications Collaborative and may include input from PREP4BLUE and/or basin CSA partners.

[Horizon Europe](#) states that it is a strategic research and innovation program that aims to give every element of society a chance to contribute to solving the planet's biggest problems, and therefore the Missions should provide a not-yet-seen opportunity for pan-European collaboration. As such, the EU Missions require communication and coordination across nearly all parts of European society, science, and economy. Subsequently, this Communication Strategy is intended for use by all Mission Ocean partners, not just those within PREP4BLUE, and over the course of the project, WP2 will solicit feedback from and work with a variety of actors involved in the Mission.

2 Distinguishing Partner Communications

It is important to distinguish the differences between the many parties who will communicate for and on behalf of Mission Ocean as they will employ different strategies and branding components. These include the PREP4BLUE CSA, the basin CSAs, other EC-funded projects, the EC itself (and its different internal sections), interested public parties (citizens, NGOs, businesses, media), etc. Through its communication activities, WP2 will attempt to work together with all relevant partners to share a wide variety of content across various channels to build a large, cohesive, engaged Mission community – and to help promote consistent branding.

2.1 PREP4BLUE & WP2

PREP4BLUE is one of many EC-funded projects under Mission Ocean, and its specific communications efforts are branded using its own PREP4BLUE graphics, templates, etc. – different from, but strategically aligned with, Mission Ocean branding created by the EC. As we anticipate that basin CSAs and forthcoming projects will also create their own branding for their specific projects, our intention is to facilitate knowledge transfer related to assets and tools so that all Mission Ocean EC-funded partners have access to the correct resources for communications related specifically to Mission Ocean. It is important for all Mission Ocean related EC-project funded partners to align their efforts and branding with Mission Ocean in order to facilitate consistent identification of Mission Ocean, which in turn facilitates wider public recognition, understanding, and engagement. Indeed, public recognition of Mission Ocean, much like the public recognizes World Wildlife Fund (WWF) or Patagonia based on imagery, slogans, etc., is very important.

PREP4BLUE has its own branding for promotion of it as a CSA, and Work Package 2 is tasked with communicating and promoting Mission Ocean, not PREP4BLUE, even though it is a PREP4BLUE work package. This creates an interesting dynamic as Mission Ocean communications need to be specifically aligned with the EC's branding and not necessarily PREP4BLUE's. This can be seen in the differences in the two websites (one for PREP4BLUE and one for Mission Ocean), use of graphics in public spheres promoting

the Mission, etc. Internally, and at events where we distinguish ourselves as the PREP4BLUE project, we would use PREP4BLUE templates, etc. with the PREP4BLUE branding. Externally via our social media and Mission Ocean website, we maintain alliance with the EC's Mission branding.

Section 2.1.1 briefly addresses PREP4BLUE tools and assets, and the remainder of this Communications Strategy focuses on communications as done through WP2 on behalf of Mission Ocean specifically, rather than PREP4BLUE as a project. The 2-page Cheat Sheet in Section 5 summarizes communications tools overall and is easily printable.

Do you want to communicate about PREP4BLUE or Mission Ocean?

Depending on your message and audience, there are different tools and platforms.

- ✓ Stakeholders should contact KDM about Mission Ocean communications.
- ✓ Partners should contact ERINN about PREP4BLUE communications.

2.1.1 PREP4BLUE Communications

“The purpose of PREP4BLUE’s communication activities is to make the project, its results and activities known to society at large so that all stakeholders, including those beyond the project’s own community, will be able to understand its messages. All PREP4BLUE partners will dedicate time to perform communication activities and will be encouraged to engage in a two-way exchange with the public at large, and where possible the media, with the aim to show how EU research and innovation funding has a positive impact on society.”¹

Whereas WP2 is specifically working toward promoting and growing the Mission Ocean community through communications work, PREP4BLUE also has a vested interest in promoting its work as a unique project, and therefore in those efforts, the PREP4BLUE tools should be used.

PREP4BLUE WP1 (Project Coordination, Synergies, Communication) created a [shared folder \(accessible ONLY to PREP4BLUE partners\) that houses documents with guidance on using PREP4BLUE branding elements](#). The same shared folder also houses all currently available Mission Ocean communications documents, images, graphics, etc., including those from the EC. They are distinguished in the folders based on this difference: PREP4BLUE vs. Mission Ocean.

2.1.1.1 Guidance Documents & Newsletter

Key documents to review when deciding how best to communicate as PREP4BLUE include the [PREP4BLUE Brand Guide](#) and the [Plan for the Dissemination and Exploitation including Communication Activities](#). All related PREP4BLUE images, graphics, templates, etc. are also housed within the shared folder.

¹ D1.2: Plan for the Dissemination and Exploitation including Communication Activities

Additionally, PREP4BLUE publishes via email a newsletter that is designed to keep partners up to date on all the latest project news, results, and updates from the project's Executive Committee.

For questions related to using PREP4BLUE materials, or the newsletter, contact T1.5 leader Cliona Ní Cheallacháin from ERINN at cliona@erinn.eu.

2.1.1.2 Websites (PREP4BLUE, Mission Ocean Waters, EC)

The PREP4BLUE website, www.prep4blue.eu, is meant to disseminate and promote PREP4BLUE results. While public, it is not specifically designed to promote Mission Ocean overall. It is distinctly separate from the WP2-created Mission Ocean website, <https://missionoceanwaters.eu>, which is specifically designed to promote Mission Ocean and engage the public as well as relevant stakeholders and Charter signatories. It is important to note that there are also [official EC webpages dedicated to Mission Ocean](#); however, they remain relatively inflexible and can't accommodate the type of content the WP2 Mission Ocean website can and will as part of its task role as a pilot website.

- After April 2023, partners/stakeholders should refer interested parties to <https://missionoceanwaters.eu> to learn about the Mission (EC webpages will link from there).
- Partners who wish to submit content to the PREP4BLUE website should contact ERINN.
- Partners who wish to submit content to the Mission Ocean website should contact KDM.

2.1.1.3 Social Media

PREP4BLUE has its own Twitter account at [@prep4blue](https://twitter.com/prep4blue). This should not be confused with WP2's Mission Ocean Waters Twitter account, [@eumissionocean](https://twitter.com/eumissionocean) (further discussed in [Section 4.2](#)).

Social networking is an integral part of the PREP4BLUE communication strategy as the project results and outputs will be actively disseminated through Twitter. Stakeholders are encouraged to follow PREP4BLUE social media, which are forums for engagement with interested parties and contribute to capacity building, showing partner expertise and knowledge through active discussions. Partners wishing to communicate via the PREP4BLUE Twitter account have the following options:

- 1) Email a short message (280 characters max) to cliona@erinn.eu who can post from the PREP4BLUE accounts on your behalf. Include an image/short video for visual appeal.
- 2) Refer to PREP4BLUE by tagging the project (using [@prep4blue](https://twitter.com/prep4blue)) in your own tweets/posts; ERINN will always aim to retweet/share such posts.
- 3) If you communicate publicly about PREP4BLUE or PREP4BLUE-related matters, you must disclose your role within the project.

2.1.1.4 Ontology

To ensure partners and even the public can understand and properly reference the various aspects of Mission Ocean, PREP4BLUE Task 4.1 will create a Mission Ontology and Semantic Network report, due in November 2023. Partners should reference this to understand and communicate Mission Ocean with respect to defined terms, relationships, etc.

See The Cheat Sheet [In Section 5](#) For A Succinct Overview Of Communications

2.2 European Commission (EC)

The EC developed a general Missions communications plan (for all five Missions), Mission guidelines, branding assets, presentations, etc. for use by funded EC projects and has shared them with PREP4BLUE and the basin CSAs. Additionally, WP2 has been encouraged by the EC to work with basin CSAs and other EC-funded partners as related to communications efforts so there is wider collaboration, understanding, and cross-pollination in the promotion of Mission Ocean. Therefore, WP2 will also house all provided relevant EC documents and assets in the PREP4BLUE shared Teams folders as well as the Mission Ocean Digital Academy (Digital Academy) on the new WP2 Mission Ocean website (accessible only to partners granted log-in access). For forthcoming funded partners who are granted access to the Digital Academy, including Charter signatories, they too will have access to the materials. Discussions about the role the Mission Ocean Implementation Support Platform (MOISP) will play in acquiring and hosting assets are ongoing.

The EC also has several social media channels and websites/webpages relevant to Mission Ocean; however, none are specifically designated to promote Mission Ocean *only*. Rather, they provide a variety of content relevant to those channels and so Mission Ocean “shares the spotlight” for attention. That is why PREP4BLUE WP2 created channels and a website dedicated solely to Mission Ocean.

While PREP4BLUE is not the official “face” of Mission Ocean, as the EC is, nonetheless, the WP2 social media Twitter channel has become a recognized voice for Mission Ocean over the past 9 months; in fact, the EC has specifically requested PREP4BLUE WP2’s presence at events to Tweet on behalf of Mission Ocean. And, ideally, as time progresses, the other WP2-created social media channels and website will become the main channels for those seeking Mission Ocean information. They will be updated regularly with important information and possess a kind of “freedom to post” that EC channels do not have due to legal and other constraints. Keeping all of this in mind, it is still important that Basin CSAs, WP organizations, other partners and stakeholders, and the public in general are aware of and follow EC/EU channels that share Mission Ocean and other related environmental information as they do remain the official face of all the Missions. The MOISP has noted that they will work with the EC to update their website to cater to those more interested in policy and data about the Mission. A nonexhaustive list of EC/EU webpages and social media channels to follow is below.

2.2.1 List of EC Promotional Materials

All partners need to be mindful of access to and permissions required for using EC-created branding materials, including graphics, noted in the table below.

- ✓ Access: All available-to-PREP4BLUE official EC guides and assets are currently housed in the PREP4BLUE shared Teams folder and will, upon the KDM Mission Ocean website’s launch, also be housed in the Digital Academy behind a log-in wall for funded partners who are authorized to view and use them. For those outside of PREP4BLUE who wish to view/use these EC files, email engage@missionoceanwaters.eu, subject line “Access EC Mission Ocean Assets”.
- ✓ Get Permission: To use official EC materials, the “Visual Representations Terms and Conditions EU Linked Parties” document needs to be signed by the leading coordinator of the organization/project and returned to EC RTD O2 (email KDM for contact information). One form

should be enough to cover all official partners within that specific project for use of the logo and assets, but this needs to be confirmed with the EC when the form is returned. You can request the form from KDM or access it in the PREP4BLUE shared Teams folder. It will also be available in the Digital Academy once live.

LIST OF EC DOCUMENTS & ASSETS (NOT EXHAUSTIVE) AVAILABLE FOR/RELATED TO MISSION OCEAN COMMUNICATIONS All files stored in the PREP4BLUE Shared Teams Folder: Communication Materials	
The Use of the Logo of the European Commission: Guidelines for Partner Organizations	
Visual Identity Guidelines for the European Missions	
Various Versions of Mission Ocean Water Drop Icons	
STRATEGIC COMMUNICATION FOR THE FIVE EU Missions - Overarching Communication Strategy & Mission specific strategic recommendations DG RTD	
Mission Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030: What's in it for me?	
Other Promotional Materials (Charter, posters, templates, presentations, fact sheets, graphics, etc.)	
Videos (via YouTube, not shared folders)	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lighthouses in Mission Ocean & Waters (current) • EU missions – Healthy oceans, seas, coastal and inland waters (old) • The ocean is our mission (old) 	

2.2.2 List of EC/EU Social Media Channels & Websites

EC/EU SOCIAL MEDIA CHANNELS RELEVANT TO MISSION OCEAN	
This list is not exhaustive and only meant to briefly illustrate accounts that post content relevant to Mission Ocean. We recommend following these channels/webpages for increased knowledge of the Missions in general and to stay abreast of current affairs, events, funding opportunities, etc.	
Twitter	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DG Research & Innovation @EUScienceInnov • Maritime Affairs & Fisheries DG MARE @EU_MARE • European Climate, Infrastructure & Environment Executive Agency CINEA @cinea_eu • EU Commission @EU Commission • Horizon Europe @HorizonEU • Sustainable Blue Economy Partnership @BlueEconomyEU • Horizon Magazine @HorizonMagEU • Commissioner @GabrielMariya

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Acting Director General @ratsosi • Director Healthy Planet, Directorate-General for Research & Innovation @bellser48 • Head of Unit Healthy Ocean & Seas @eli_balzi • UN Ocean Decade @UNOceanDecade (not an EC/EU site)
Facebook	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU Science & Innovation • European Commission • European Research Council • CORDIS EU • UN Sustainable Development Platform (*not an EU platform)
YouTube	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU Science & Innovation @EUScienceInnovation • EUtube @European Commission • View more EU YouTube Channels
Hashtags	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Official Mission Ocean: #MissionOcean, #HorizonEU, #EUmissions (these 3 should always be used when posting about Mission Ocean) • Lighthouses: #bluemissionmed (Mediterranean Lighthouse), #BlueMissionBANOS (Baltic & North Sea Lighthouse), #bluemissionaa (Arctic/Atlantic Lighthouse), #bluemissionecodalli • Other relevant ocean/environment topics to follow: #BlueEconomy #EUGreenDeal, #EU, #SaveOurOcean, #OceanScience, #BlueTransition #EUHaveYourSay, #NewEuropeanBauhaus, #UNOceanDecade, #SDG14, #AtlanticAll #Lighthouses #oceanplastic
EC/EU WEBPAGES RELEVANT TO MISSION OCEAN	
Webpages	<p>While the EC does not have a website specifically dedicated to Mission Ocean, they do have the webpages noted below. We recommend all stakeholders regularly check them for updated information. Once live, the KDM Mission Ocean website will also link to the main EC Mission Ocean webpage.</p> <p>Main EC Mission Ocean Webpage: EU Mission: Restore our Ocean and Waters</p> <p>Page Contents:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What is the Mission? • Mission Charter <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Charter Signatories & Actions Interactive Map • Funding opportunities • What are EU Missions? • More information • Contact • Documents • Latest • Events

	Interested parties should also refer to Horizon Europe .
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2.3 Project Partners

At the time of this deliverable’s due date, the Mission Ocean Implementation Support Platform (MOISP) and basic CSAs have only recently been selected and begun their work. How they will develop their communications strategies, content, tools, assets, etc. hasn’t yet been shared with WP2; this would include any of their own specific branding, etc. However, as PREP4BLUE is meant to provide tools and resources for these groups, our intent is to actively involve a representative from each basin CSA and other EC-funded Mission Ocean partners in the Communications Collaborative for bi-monthly meetings to share tools, assets, and resources. Thus far, both the Mediterranean and the Atlantic representatives were invited to the group’s first meeting and all basin CSAs were included in the second meeting. The Communications Collaborative will continue to evolve as the MOISP is further integrated into the Mission.

We always encourage basin CSAs and other project partners to reach out to KDM to share information, and we welcome other partners who may want to join the Communications Collaborative to contact us. We also recommend all Mission Ocean stakeholders follow the Lighthouses on their social media and website platforms; their available information is in the table below.

MISSION OCEAN LIGHTHOUSES – PUBLIC PLATFORMS	
BlueMissionAA (Atlantic & Arctic Ocean)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website: https://bluemissionaa.eu • Facebook: https://facebook.com/bluemissionaa • Instagram: https://instagram.com/bluemissionaa • Twitter: https://twitter.com/bluemissionaa • LinkedIn: https://linkedin.com/company/bluemissionaa • Mastodon: https://ohai.social/@bluemissionaa • YouTube: https://youtube.com/@bluemissionaa • Hashtag: #bluemissionaa • Email: bluemissionaa@aircentre.org
BlueMissionMed (Mediterranean Sea)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website: https://bluemissionmed.eu/ • Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/bluemissionmed • Instagram: https://www.instagram.com/bluemissionmed/ • Twitter: https://twitter.com/bluemissionmed • LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/company/blue-mission-med/ • Hashtag: #bluemissionmed
BlueMissionBANOS (Baltic & North Sea)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website: http://bluemissionbanos.eu • Twitter: https://twitter.com/MissionBANOS • LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/company/missionbanos/ • Hashtag: #bluemissionbanos
BlueMissionEcoDaLLi (Danube River)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/company/ecodalli-project/ • Hashtag: #ecodalli

2.4 The Public

A major component of PREP4BLUE is citizen/stakeholder engagement (led by other WPs), and WP2 is committed to engaging in communications activities to help further the success of those efforts. Our website, social media channels, and events are all geared toward engaging not only official partners, but also the public. Furthermore, through the Communications Collaborative, we are actively seeking content from the WPs engaged in these tasks to promote their relevant activities, events, etc. As time goes on, our communications and outreach activities will more actively solicit content and engagement directly from the public via our social media campaign, MoJo efforts, and two public events. At this initial stage (year 1), we will rely on information gathered from WP3, WP4, and WP6 as well as the basin CSAs to feed us appropriate information for sharing.

3 Communicating Mission Ocean

3.1 Mission Ocean Narratives

3.1.1 D2.1 - Narrative Guide

WP2 Deliverable 2.1 is a Narrative Guide that provides key information on Mission Ocean narratives. It can be accessed in the [PREP4BLUE shared Teams folder](#), or for those without Teams access, requested via email to KDM. For the purposes of this communication strategy, we'll briefly highlight key narrative information for enhanced communication of the Mission below, but in-depth information should be accessed via the Narrative Guide.

3.1.2 Narrative Overview & Application

3.1.2.1 What is a "narrative"?

A narrative is a form of storytelling that can shape opinions and understandings of reality. It can be used as a tool to construct people's perspectives and alter relationships. Consequently, fiction and myths can become fact in many minds, and – vice versa, fact can become fiction. Narratives are, therefore, powerful in their influential nature, often regardless of their truth. For our purposes, we are committed to sharing a truthful narrative that inspires our audience to engage in and commit to the Mission, in any way they may be able (signing the Charter, organizing local activities, making life choices, etc.). Our communications activities should always adhere to the overarching narratives relevant to Mission Ocean.

3.1.2.2 What is the Mission Ocean narrative?

When creating narratives through stories, it's important to develop specific messages for each objective/audience combination and to then adapt them to specific channels (social media, website, event, etc.). Concerning the ocean, the dominant narrative focusing on sustainable human ocean interactions is based on the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) of the United Nations. At the EU-level, the focus has been on the EU Green Deal and its goals. From this has been distilled the three goals for the Mission Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030:

- Protect and restore marine and freshwater ecosystems and biodiversity, in line with the EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030
- Prevent and eliminate pollution of our ocean, seas and waters, in line with the EU Action Plan Towards Zero Pollution for Air, Water and Soil
- Make the sustainable blue economy carbon-neutral and circular, in line with the proposed European Climate Law and the holistic vision enshrined in the Sustainable Blue Economy Strategy

With three goals being addressed through hundreds of millions of Euros in funding across numerous projects, we must acknowledge that Mission Ocean is so large and vast that implying there is only one story to tell, one overarching message, would underserve its many ambitions. There are a number of narratives that can be used as part of Mission Ocean but, as no resource is as precious or valuable to life on earth as water, we need everyone to understand THAT concept. Therefore, the overarching focus should always be on ***“fostering awe around the ocean and our waters - inspiring respect and commitment to its health not only through the Charter and its goals, but through every-day actions that everybody can take to support the Mission.”*** We are focused on advocating for ***pristine, protected, and prosperous*** ocean and waters, as they tie into the three goals of the Mission. And, our messaging should always strive to promote an end toward those values and goals via understanding, acceptance, and support of Mission Ocean overall. In fact, in a [video made from the Sessions from the European Research and Innovation days in 2020](#), Pascal Lamy (minute 6:50) says we need to address the very big problem that is this gap between the importance of oceans and waters on the one side and the very little knowledge and emotional connection that many people have with them.

3.1.2.3 My Mission, Our Mission, EU Mission

Our role as official partners of the Mission is to inspire European communities, organizations, stakeholders, businesses, citizens, etc. toward achieving essential common goals by involving them directly in their design, implementation, and assessment. Our EC-funded Mission Ocean partner community, including PREP4BLUE as well as the Lighthouses and other entities, can and should include everyone as our ocean and waters serve everyone. Therefore, our narratives will be structured through 3 levels: EU Mission, Our Mission, and My Mission – each telling stories through the lens of those audiences and stakeholders.

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3.1.2.4 Engagement Goals

Our role in WP2 will be to help promote the narratives via our communications tools, resources, and platforms (noted later in this document). Whether utilizing the website to feature stories, social media to promote videos, or events to reach the masses, we can utilize a number of narratives and meet our engagement goals to:

- Foster knowledge, acceptance, and support of the Mission to facilitate its success
- Inspire and foster awareness across all audiences to bolster citizen engagement
- Encourage signing the Mission Charter (for legal entities only) to commit businesses and organizations to change
- Create a new way of working together (everyone is invited; this is a collaboration, not a competition) to escape stagnant situations and relationships
- Spotlight Mission activities/work for increased confidence and positive perceptions surrounding Mission Ocean and its EC funding
- Encourage attendance at Mission events (citizen assemblies, workshops, trainings, etc.) for increased public participation/citizen awareness and engagement
- Spread the word about funding to engage businesses and organizations - fostering innovation, engagement, and economic stimulus
- Collect and share data to promote appropriate marine science integration and shared knowledge
- Spotlight various interesting Mission Ocean subjects (new technology, projects, people doing good works, marine creatures, etc.) to foster knowledge and awareness amongst the public and other stakeholders for increased interest in marine issues

- Create awareness and/or activism around an issue (plastic pollution, deep sea mining, sustainable fishing, daily personal choices, etc.) to drive personal accountability, investment, and dedication to the cause

3.1.2.5 Storytelling

Imagine what we could accomplish if everyone who hears our message were to join Mission Ocean and commit to it achieving its goals. For this reason, we want to tell inspirational stories and to be the visionary leaders who inspire everyone on behalf of Mission Ocean.

The following storytelling prompts could contribute to our overarching narratives and goals:

STORYTELLING PROMPTS TO CREATE NARRATIVES (types of content we will actively solicit from partners & stakeholders)	POTENTIAL INFLUENCE ON MISSION AWARENESS, PERCEPTION, & RELATIONSHIPS
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Who has signed the Charter and why (profiles, sectors, testimonies)? • What are they doing to meet their commitments? • Which companies are funded under Mission Ocean and doing the “boots on the ground” work? • What exactly are they doing? • Ocean Superstars: who’s who and who’s doing what for the health of our ocean and waters? 	<p>Demonstrate community, business, and organizational support and commit to the Mission.</p> <p>Profiling businesses with different business models based on nature-based solutions making an actual impact may inspire local communities to engage. It could also enhance business opportunities and successes.</p> <p>Upsell the idea of becoming an ocean celebrity, inspiring pride in being part of Mission Ocean and engaging all audiences on a wider level to contribute and share.</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What are the “Lighthouses” and what are they doing? • How will they help meet the three goals? 	<p>Spotlight successful funding campaigns making a real difference on the ground – demonstrating the Mission’s viability and importance in our future.</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What are European Blue Parks? • How do they benefit me/us/society/the world? • Is there one I can visit? 	<p>Engage the public in visiting and appreciating our ocean and water environments, inspiring awe and wonder, encouraging tourism and activism, and facilitating genuine care for our environment.</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What defines “good ocean/water/ecosystem health” and which areas are healthy vs. unhealthy? • What’s involved in restoring marine and freshwater ecosystems, and how can I contribute/support these initiatives? 	<p>Expand public knowledge, increase awareness, and build confidence to contribute to public actions toward more healthy ecosystems.</p>

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learn about series (fisheries, algae production, sea creatures, bio-based solutions, etc.) • Which movies can I watch to learn more about the ocean and waters? • What can I do in my daily life to help as “just one person”? 	
<p>What actions are being taken at the national, regional, or organization level to prevent/minimize/remediate marine/freshwater pollution?</p>	<p>Build confidence in the EU/EC efforts, including funding programs under Mission Ocean to foster public buy-in and appreciate the spending/funding commitment.</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What is a “blue economy”? • Who does it affect financially, and how does it work? • How are investors shifting towards green/blue investing? • Which areas are being affected by sea level rise and what are the socio-economic impacts? 	<p>Foster knowledge and understanding about the real-world implications of how our ocean and waters are used and the financial impacts to every segment of society, thereby increasing awareness and public care for the blue economy.</p>
<p>What are the latest advances in “blue tech” and “big blue data” (biodiversity/pollution monitoring, European Digital Twin Ocean, tools and gadgets, etc.)?</p>	<p>Demonstrate interesting and captivating tech and information to drive public and stakeholder excitement around ocean industry.</p>
<p>What are the other Missions and how do they interact with Mission Ocean?</p>	<p>Expand awareness of the Missions – potentially reaching a much more diverse audience who may find a link to Mission Ocean through other Missions, and vice versa.</p>

3.2 Work with WP2 to Communicate Mission Ocean

<p>PROTOCOL</p> <p>All Mission Ocean contributors, from funded partners to the public, are encouraged to share their Mission Ocean related events, success stories, data, pictures, videos, etc. with us for promotion across our channels. Indeed, communicating Mission Ocean has to be a collaborative effort, and its success will in part depend on the willingness of partners to provide content. Contact KDM for more information.</p>
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A key component of our communication strategy is to co-develop content and stories through ongoing engagement with partners and stakeholders. A large portion of this will be done through the

Communications Collaborative, via official Mission events, and from our partners via direct outreach. As we understand it, standard top-down, one-to-many communication is not the best approach, so novel and innovative ways for soliciting content as well as communicating with citizens and stakeholders to achieve our goals is paramount. Therefore, a unique strategy will be applied to each targeted audience, using appropriate messages on the appropriate channel(s). This will be developed in concert with our contracted social media expert, Joanne Sweeney from the Digital Training Institute in Ireland, to help us successfully solicit and then promote such things as Charter signatories, funded projects, events, news, videos, campaigns, etc. Our goals also include reaching and growing our audience types and members to facilitate understanding, acceptance, and support of Mission Ocean.

Our aim is to provide information that is:

- 1) Authentic and realistic, appropriately reflecting the efforts being made to overcome whatever challenges exist to achieving the three Mission goals.
- 2) Content-focused, emphasizing “scalable and replicable, excellent and impact-driven research and innovation solutions (technological, business, social and governance) and demonstration activities”.
- 3) Community-oriented, reflecting the “basin-wide cooperation, commitment and deployment of solutions” in each of the Lighthouse areas.
- 4) Inclusive and diverse, incorporating tried and tested deliberative democracy mechanisms and social innovation practices, participatory governance approaches, mobilizing and empowering citizens for the co-design and co-implementation of solutions.

Successful Mission Ocean communications rely on all partners providing diverse content with multiple narratives to drive engagement across various channels.

WP2 will be happy to work with partners on the following activities in the shaping and planning of communications that are relevant for our platforms and channels.

- Establishing Goals

Referring back to Engagement Goals and the narratives, we have to consider what exactly we are trying to do, not only with others' communications, but with projects as well. It is not enough to say, "we want to reach 100 people." We will clarify exactly what that reach entails and why it matters.

- **Knowing & Understanding the Audience**

Knowing and understanding our audience can help us determine the kind of content and messaging they care about as well as the appropriate tone and voice of the message to best reach them. It's also essential for the channel and graphics used. When considering our communications, we will decide:

- Who is my target audience?
- Where are they?
- How old are they?
- How educated are they?
- Are they a partner, a stakeholder, a member of the public, a business, etc.?
- What is their political persuasion?
- Are they already active in the water/environmental arena or new to the scene?
- Do they respond to articles or short videos? Memes or striking photographs?
- Are they easily influenced or skeptical of the media?
- How can I most effectively get them to engage with this message?

These questions can help form the basis of a targeted campaign to better reach people and effect change.

- **Creating an Outreach Plan**

An outreach plan documents ways to share information with the audience we're targeting. What is the end goal? What are we trying to accomplish with this messaging? Is it to share the good news, inform and educate, inspire activism, or something else? Our messaging needs to have a purpose so that we identify the correct ways to achieve that purpose. Again, this should be done in reflection of the narratives and engagement goals.

When creating an initial outreach plan, we will:

- Identify the needs/wants – what are we trying to do through this effort? Why?
- Clarify the issue/subject
- Set a realistic yet ambitious goal for the outcome of the message
- Determine our audience and stakeholders
- Develop a tailored strategy for sharing – who, when, where, how
- Craft and refine the message(s)
- Share/post
- Monitor and engage with the feedback for continued relationship building

**Normally we would also include as a final step "measure for success". However, measuring communications success is not in WP2's tasks and deliverables, although a mid-term status report will address milestones and successes to some extent. Some communications KPIs are part of other WPs.*

4 Tools & Resources

WP2 will provide specific tools and resources for Mission Ocean partners to aid in their communications efforts. As part of our pilot initiative, it is our hope these aid in promoting understanding and support of, commitment to, and engagement with the Mission.

4.1 Website

A dedicated Mission Ocean website, <https://missionoceanwaters.eu>, will be launched shortly after the time this deliverable is submitted. As part of our pilot initiatives designed to do things in a less traditional way, it takes a unique and fun approach to sharing Mission Ocean through a number of technologies, including breathtaking drone video footage, interactive dialogue, personal testimonials, and helpful information such as news, events, stories, etc. The website is also set to host a Mission Ocean Digital Academy behind a log-in with training videos, a toolkit, and access to documents and assets for official partners, among other helpful items.

The website’s core menu will highlight interactive content.

MISSION OCEAN WEBSITE FEATURES	
Partners are requested to include a link to the website on their own organization’s website. https://missionoceanwaters.eu	
Home	Home will consist of four separate Lighthouse pages
About	Focus on the “EU Mission” - A descriptive page with links to official pages, a calendar, background information, and more
Explore	Focus on “Our Mission” with an overview of all contributions to the Mission, esp. EU funded projects as well as national and local contributions (e.g., Charter signatories)
Contribute	Focus on “My Mission” with an overview of citizen science activities (e.g., Plastic Pirates) and testimonials
Mission Ocean Digital Academy	A service to the Mission community with social media trainings esp. for Charter signatories, Lighthouses, Mission projects, etc.

Each of the Lighthouses will be represented by a “scene” (see picture below) intended to showcase the Lighthouse and contributing individuals and activities. These scenes will employ descriptive and viewpoint

narratives with the aim to “emotionalize” the Mission through interactive elements which involve the user and are meant to be fun. The user is immersed, and they interact with people, their surroundings, products, and objects, and experience first-hand brands and events.

Lighthouse webpage example screenshots

4.2 Social Media

To date, WP2 has established seven social media channels to promote the work of Mission Ocean specifically and to help build an engaged community – for the public and partners. These channels will continue to exist over the course of the 3-year PREP4BLUE contract with the hope that, as Mission Ocean continues to 2030 and PREP4BLUE ends, the channels will somehow be maintained and continue to grow. As PREP4BLUE is the first official CSA charged with building the Mission Ocean community, maintaining the channels for the duration of the Mission project through 2030 will not be possible unless the contract is extended, or other ways are found. We strongly recommend they are managed through the Mission duration, and possibly even after, especially as they have established themselves as some of the main platforms for Mission Ocean and ocean/water information in general.

While we are eager to share partner, stakeholder, and even public Mission-related information, stories, events, etc., we will actively manage and determine which information is appropriate for our channels based on social media best practices and relevance. We strive to have our posts:

- Inspire, educate, inform, or propose a call to action
- Stay professional (no illegal or dishonest content)
- Contain working links and captivating imagery or videos
- Use appropriate tags, hashtags, and references, including crediting creators

Additionally, KDM has contracted with the Digital Training Institute in Ireland to help manage social media, work with mobile journalists, and provide content for our new Mission Ocean Digital Academy through 2023. Any questions or comments about these channels should be emailed to KDM.

4.2.2 Social Media Pilot Campaign

We will hold a focus group with PREP4BLUE partners and/or Mission Ocean stakeholders to brainstorm ideas for the pilot social media campaign after the first Mission Ocean Forum in February 2023 with the intent of launching the campaign in mid-late 2023.

Here is a sample campaign and how we would approach it.

I. Campaign goal and objectives

- The goal of the campaign is to raise awareness about the importance of ocean conservation and inspire people to take action to protect and preserve our oceans.
- The objectives of the campaign are to:
 - Increase the number of followers on our social media platforms by at least 20%
 - Generate at least 500 shares of campaign-related content
 - Encourage at least 50% of followers to take a specific action (e.g., sign a petition, donate to a conservation organization, participate in a beach clean-up)

II. Target audience

- The target audience for the campaign is young adults aged 18-35 with a focus on students and recent graduates who are passionate about environmental issues and interested in learning more about ocean conservation.

III. Campaign theme and messaging

- The campaign theme is "Our Ocean, Our Future: Take Action Now"
- The messaging for the campaign will focus on the urgent need to protect and preserve our oceans for future generations, highlighting the many ways in which our oceans support life on earth and the impact of human activities on the health of our oceans.

IV. Social media content and tactics

- To drive engagement and reach, the campaign will use a variety of social media content and tactics, including:
 - Inspiring and informative posts about the importance of ocean conservation
 - Infographics and other visual content to make complex information more accessible and engaging
 - Interactive content such as polls, quizzes, and live Q&A sessions with ocean experts
 - User-generated content, such as photos and videos of people taking action for the oceans (e.g., participating in a beach clean-up, reducing plastic use)
 - Collaborations with influencers and other organizations to amplify the campaign message and reach a wider audience

V. Campaign timeline and metrics

- The campaign will run for a period of one month with a strong push in the first week to create initial buzz and momentum.
- Key metrics for the campaign will include:
 - Increase in social media followers

- Number of shares and engagement with campaign-related content
- Number of people taking the desired action (e.g., signing a petition, donating to a conservation organization, participating in a beach clean-up)

VI. Evaluation and next steps

- At the end of the campaign, we will assess the success of the campaign and identify any areas for improvement.
- Based on the results of the campaign, we will develop a plan for ongoing ocean activism and outreach efforts, including identifying new opportunities for collaboration and engagement with our followers.

4.3 Mission Ocean Digital Academy

The Mission Ocean Digital Academy will be created in order to develop an accessible and scalable digital skills academy for Mission Ocean partners, including Charter signatories, to extend the reach of the Mission's message and to upskill project teams on best practice social media and digital communications. Our goal with the Digital Academy is to further enable our partners in their capacity to share and promote Mission Ocean and all the good it does. We expect to launch the initial phase in late April 2023 when the website also officially launches.

The Digital Academy platform includes a desktop and mobile Learning Management System which is only accessible by being granted log-in details by the administrator/s. The log-in will live on the Mission Ocean website.

Who Can Access It?

- PREP4BLUE and basin CSAs partners
- Mission Ocean Charter signatories
- Other relevant EC-funded Mission Ocean partners

Why Join?

Partners will be invited to join the Digital Academy in order to:

- Inspire them to communicate their committed actions across digital channels
- Show them how to develop a social media campaign
- Upskill their team
- Amplify the work of Mission Ocean and partners
- Access important documents, tools, and resources/assets

4.3.1 Digital Academy Resources

The Digital Academy will offer many resources, including:

1. Social Media Toolkit and Campaign Blueprint - a step-by-step guide on how to:
 - a. Prepare their social media campaign concept
 - b. Set goals and key performance indicators
 - c. Identify target audiences
 - d. Engage partners to amplify your campaign

- e. Choose relevant digital channels
 - f. Craft campaign messages
 - g. Write engaging copy for posts
 - h. Create content - videos, graphics, animations, go live
 - i. Develop a content calendar
 - j. Create an implementation plan
 - k. Measure and report
2. Trello Board for Mission Ocean content which partners can take and share on their own social networks (see the UN Ocean Decade Trello example at <https://trello.com/b/Oozo52UM/oceandecade>)
 3. Tutorial/How-To Videos/Checklists - to complement the social media campaign blueprint to help project teams manage social media in accordance with best practices and teach them new skills
 4. Graphic Templates - a suite of template graphics for project teams to use on their own social media campaigns
 5. PREP4BLUE Social Media Campaign Case Study - a written and video case study on how PREP4BLUE's signature social media campaign was devised and implemented, acting as both an inspiration and learnings tool
 6. Ocean Advocacy Campaigns on Social Media - exploring six examples of viral social media campaigns about ocean conservation:
 - I. The Cove (2009) - This documentary film about the hunting of dolphins in Japan became a viral sensation on social media, leading to widespread outrage and calls for action to protect dolphins and other marine wildlife.
 - II. #SavetheMed (2013) - This social media campaign, organized by the Mediterranean Sea Preservation Society, aimed to raise awareness about the environmental threats facing the Mediterranean Sea and encourage people to take action to protect it. The campaign used hashtags, videos, and other content to engage people on social media and drive action.
 - III. #PassOnPlastic (2017) - This campaign, launched by Sky Ocean Rescue, aimed to raise awareness about the impact of plastic pollution on the oceans and encourage people to reduce their use of single-use plastics. The campaign used a combination of social media content and traditional media to reach a wide audience and drive action.
 - IV. #SeaTurtlesSelfie (2018) - This social media campaign, organized by the Sea Turtle Conservancy, aimed to raise awareness about the threats facing sea turtles and encourage people to take action to protect them. The campaign used the hashtag #SeaTurtlesSelfie to encourage people to share photos of themselves with sea turtle-themed props, as well as other content about sea turtle conservation.
 - V. #SeaYourself (2019) - This campaign, organized by the World Wildlife Fund (WWF), aimed to raise awareness about the importance of protecting our oceans and the incredible wildlife that lives there. The campaign used the hashtag #SeaYourself to encourage people to share photos of themselves with ocean-themed props and other content about ocean conservation.
 - VI. TikTok #SaveOurOceans Campaign (2019)- The campaign was a partnership between TikTok and Conservation International, with the goal of raising awareness about the importance of ocean conservation and inspiring people to take action to protect and

preserve our oceans. TikTok users could apply an ocean effect to their videos and virtually "clean plastic" out of the ocean. For every video uploaded with the hashtag #SaveOurOceans, TikTok donated \$2 to Conservation International, with a goal of raising up to \$100,000 to help save 3,000 square kilometers of ocean. The campaign was open to users in a number of countries and regions, including the US, the UK, France, Spain, Italy, and more. The campaign aimed to address the global plastic pollution crisis, which is a major threat to the health of the oceans and the wildlife that lives there. Scientists predict that the weight of ocean plastics will exceed the combined weight of all fish in the seas by 2050. The campaign aims to educate and inspire TikTok users to take action to protect the oceans and will use the platform's global community to raise awareness and drive action.

Mission Ocean Digital Academy landing page example

EU MISSIONS
RESTORE OUR OCEAN AND WATERS

Home Templates Checklists 365 Post Ideas Tutorial Videos Audit Tools Strategy

Hashtag Checklist

A hashtag is a word or phrase preceded by a hash sign (#), used on social media and on website copy, to identify specific topics. A hashtag does not have spaces, emojis or special characters.

The purpose of a hashtag is to index keywords or topics on social networks. Hashtags were first created on Twitter and they allow people to easily follow topics that they are interested in.

This checklist is a best practice guide on how to use hashtags, how many to use across each social network and other considerations.

Watch Tutorial Video

Watch the tutorial video below to learn how to use this resource.

Download PDF Checklist

Hashtag Checklist

Checklists

- Hashtag Checklist ✓
- Social Video Checklist
- Social Listening Checklist

EU MISSIONS
RESTORE OUR OCEAN & WATERS
Concrete solutions for our greatest challenges

#EMissions #HorizonEU #MissionOcean

Cookies

Mission Ocean Digital Academy checklist page example

4.4 MoJo

MoJo stands for mobile journalism/journalist and WP2 expects to contract with 10 MoJo Creators strategically located at key areas (Lighthouses, key events, etc.) around Europe. The Role of Mission Ocean MoJo Creators is two-fold:

1. Create unique social media content for the PREP4BLUE social media campaign
2. Capture content for the Mission Ocean social networks

Targeting early career ocean scientists and ambassadors (aged 25 and under), we will invite interested young people to pitch to become part of our MoJo content creation team for:

- €500 to create 10 videos about Mission Ocean between February - July 2023
- Training and mentoring with Joanne Sweeney, Digital Marketing expert
- Access to the Mission Ocean Digital Academy
- Profiling of them on the official website/social networks
- Credited for their content
- Networking with Mission Ocean partners

4.5 Images

As noted previously, the EC created its own official Mission branding, including graphics and photos. WP2 will use official graphics in its Mission Ocean resources and will also use additional original photos and graphics to expand our visionary appeal.

All currently available image assets can be found in the PREP4BLUE shared Teams folder and will also be made available in the Digital Academy.

WP2 continues to work with the EC to set up a formal structure for information sharing related to Mission Ocean graphics, videos, documents, etc. as they are created so that they may be shared with the official partners as well as used in the social media campaigns, on the website, etc. This is still a work in progress and may later be influenced by the Mission Ocean Implementation Support Platform (MOISP)'s efforts.

4.6 Print

At this time, there is no plan for WP2 to develop paper print materials for distribution in relation to Mission Ocean. Any and all print materials to be used have either already been created by, or will in the future come from, the European Commission or its contracted partners (VO, the MOISP, etc.). As the project unfolds over the course of the next two years, this strategy could evolve or change to include printed materials for WP2's hosted events.

PREP4BLUE partners can access existing presentation, poster, and other materials that may be printed or used in the PREP4BLUE shared Teams folder. These will also be made available in the Digital Academy.

4.7 Events

WP2 will conceptualize, design, and pilot with potential venues (e.g., museums and aquariums) from around the world physical Mission spaces that serve to exhibit Mission contributions and as venues to hold Mission-related activities (e.g., citizen assemblies, foresight workshops, future labs, etc.) in Europe. Close cooperation with the Mission Secretariat, Mission Ocean Implementation Support Platform (MOISP), basin CSAs, and other relevant actors will be essential in late 2023-2024 to develop the events. The events will likely happen in 2024-2025.

5 Communication Strategy Cheat Sheet

Refer to this table for succinct information on communications related tools and resources for Mission Ocean and PREP4BLUE.

All Mission Ocean stakeholders are welcome and encouraged to contact KDM to share Mission related events, success stories, charter commitments, profiles, new technology stories, data, links, etc. for promotion across our Mission Ocean communications channels.			
TOOL/ASSET	HOW TO USE	WHO TO CONTACT	LOCATION/LINK
WP2 Mission Ocean Social Media Channels	<p>Daily updates with important information and calls to action – partners are invited to share content with us for promotion on our channels, share our posts, tag us, and link relevant sites in promotional material.</p> <p>Hashtags include: #MissionOcean, #HorizonEU, and #EUMissions and when appropriate #PREP4BLUE or the relevant Lighthouse (#bluemissionaa, #bluemissionmed, #bluemissionbanos, etc.), org, etc.)</p> <p>Refer to the Digital Academy for more Information on using social media.</p>	<p>KDM: engage@missionoceanwaters.eu</p>	<p>Twitter: @missionoceanwaters @eumissionocean Facebook: missionoceanwaters LinkedIn: Mission Ocean YouTube: MissionOceanWaters @missionoceanwaters1511 Instagram: @missionoceaneu TikTok: @missionoceanwaters Pinterest: @MissionOceanWaters</p>
Mission Ocean Website	<p>Promote events, success stories, Charter signatories, Lighthouses, related projects, stakeholders, citizen engagement; provide captivating videos and images, data; access Mission Ocean Digital Academy, social media wall, etc.</p>	<p>KDM: engage@missionoceanwaters.eu</p>	<p>https://missionoceanwaters.eu/</p>
Events (2)	<p>We will pilot with organizations (e.g., museums, aquariums, etc.) to exhibit Mission contributions and serve as venues to hold Mission-related activities (e.g., citizen assemblies, foresight workshops, future labs, etc.) in Europe.</p>	<p>KDM: engage@missionoceanwaters.eu</p>	<p>TBD 2024 with Mission Secretariat, basin CSAs, MOISP, EC, etc.</p>

Digital Academy	The Digital Academy will allow PREP4BLUE partners, Mission Ocean Charter signatories, Basin CSA partners, and other relevant EC-funded partners exclusive access to tools and instruction from Joanne Sweeney of the Digital Training Institute in order to help better communicate their actions across digital channels, develop social media campaigns, upskill their teams, and amplify the work on behalf Mission Ocean.	KDM: engage@missionoceanwaters.eu	www.Missionoceanwaters.eu Log-in access only (granted to official partners)
MoJo	We are actively seeking mobile journalists to create unique social media video content for the social media campaign and to capture content for the Mission Ocean social networks, especially TikTok and YouTube.	KDM: engage@missionoceanwaters.eu	To be stationed at Basin CSA Locations – names/contact info TBA mid-late 2023
Official EC Documents & Assets	All of the tools and assets shared with PREP4BLUE by the EC, such as brand guidelines, the EC Missions communications plan, fact sheets, PowerPoint presentations, graphics, etc. are available for immediate download by PREP4BLUE partners. They will also be available to other Mission Ocean EC-funded partners on the missionoceanwaters.eu website behind the log-in (only granted to certain partners who must adhere to official EC guidelines when using & have proper authorization via the Permission Form)	KDM: engage@missionoceanwaters.eu	Inside Prepr4Blue shared Teams folder (accessible only to PREP4BLUE partners) and inside the Digital Academy on https://missionoceanwaters.eu (log-in access only, granted to official partners)
PREP4BLUE Materials	PREP4BLUE branded assets and tools (templates, graphics, guidance documents, etc.) are for PREP4BLUE partners to use when promoting PREP4BLUE or Mission Ocean in their official PREP4BLUE project capacity. As more tools and assets are created, they will be added to the shared PREP4BLUE Teams folder for easy access by all partners.	ERINN – Cliona Ní Cheallacháin from WP4: cliona@erinn.eu OR Ifremer - Eirini Apazoglou from WP1: eirini@euromarinework.eu	Inside PREP4BLUE shared Teams folder (accessible only to PREP4BLUE partners) <ul style="list-style-type: none">• PREP4BLUE Brand Guide• Plan for the Dissemination and Exploitation including Communication Activities• Ontology coming 11/23• PREP4BLUE Website• PREP4BLUE Twitter

6 Conclusion

As is the goal of the Mission to build on and connect the many existing projects and initiatives at the EU, national, and local levels, it is also the goal of PREP4BLUE and WP2 to foster collaboration amongst our many audiences through effective communication. Our strategy revolves around creating effective tools and resources, and working with a variety of stakeholders to help ensure, on behalf of the Mission, that communications are engaging and on brand. All this while also inspiring awe and wonder around the ocean, connecting people with things they deeply value while welcoming and eliciting interest in taking action.

WP2's tools and resources can be used as part of the broader communication, dissemination, and exploitation strategies of all official partners. By utilizing our social media, website, events, and Digital Academy, our partners should be enabled to foster increased reach, engagement, understanding of, and commitment to "Mission Restore our Oceans and Waters by 2030". Additionally, partners and stakeholders should be able to better meet the expectations of the EC in terms of branding and cohesion. We therefore encourage all partners to use our tools and resources in their communications efforts and to involve PREP4BLUE WP leaders when developing communications and outreach activities as part of the broader Mission strategy to mobilize and engage the public. We welcome content for sharing!

As the first CSA funded to help facilitate a successful first phase (2022-2025) of Mission Ocean, we are hopeful our efforts will help Mission Lighthouses and other partners to develop and pilot innovative new approaches to communications and engagement that will allow co-design and co-implementation of solutions with citizens and stakeholders.